

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM ION WITH CADION IREA REAGENT

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Abstract: The determination of cadmium ions in environmental samples is an extremely important task, for which a spectrophotometric method is proposed in the research work. Cadion IREA is proposed as an analytical sensitive reagent for the determination of cadmium ions. The reflectance spectra of cadmium ions with Cadion IREA reagent were obtained on an EMC-30PC-UV-1800 Spectrophotometer.

Key words: cadmium, cadion IREA, reagent, spectrophotometric, complex.

Introduction. The rapid increase in the world population is currently leading to the development of industrial sectors. In the course of industrial processes, humans cause unprecedented damage to the environment. Various harmful components such as pharmaceuticals, pesticides, surfactants, acids, detergents, dyes and toxic metals are resources that pose an ecological risk to humans, plants and animals [1]. Cadmium is an extremely dangerous heavy metal. Depending on its chemical composition, cadmium accumulates in the liver, kidneys and other organs or tissues. Cadmium (Cd) accumulates in the human body through two main routes: inhalation and ingestion. The main sources of Cd poisoning are plants or fish rich in it. Many global organizations are working to set specific limits for the concentration of heavy metals in food, water and the environment to prevent their harmful effects. High concentrations of Cd can lead to the development of kidney, liver or brain diseases. Cadmium accumulates mainly in the kidneys, resulting in kidney disease in those exposed to moderate to high concentrations. This effect can ultimately lead to the development of end-stage chronic kidney disease or even death [2-5]. Heavy metals not only affect living organisms, but also have a significant impact on plants. Due to the introduction of heavy metals into the environment, human activities pose a greater threat to the ecosystem than natural phenomena. Cadmium concentrations above 0.3 mg/kg in soil significantly affect plant growth and development [6]. [7] Plant roots take up Cd, which is highly absorbable by living organisms, using apoplastic and symplastic pathways. It is then transported to the shoots via the xylem with the help of transporters. From there, it is transported through the phloem to the edible parts of the plant. The absorption and accumulation of cadmium (Cd) in plants has a detrimental effect on the physiological and biochemical functions of plants, leading to changes in

the structure of their vegetative and reproductive components. The toxic effect of cadmium metal makes it necessary to constantly monitor its content in environmental samples.

Methods: There are currently many methods for determining the amount of cadmium (II) ions in environmental samples, but their several shortcomings limit their scope of application. Currently, spectroscopic methods are widely used in the determination of heavy metals. We also developed a method for spectrophotometric determination of cadmium ions in our research work. Cadion IREA was chosen as an organic reagent for this. The reflectance spectra of cadmium ions with Cadion IREA reagent were measured relative to a reference solution on an EMC-30PC-UV-1800 Spectrophotometer.

1-picute. 1- cadion IREA $\lambda_{max}=410$; 2-cadion IREA +Cd²⁺ $\lambda_{max}=490$

The results show that the wavelength of blue Cadion IREA is $\lambda_{max}=410$; the wavelength of its complex with cadmium ions is $\lambda=490$. It can be seen that the difference in wavelengths is $\Delta\lambda =80$ nm. The contrast of the reaction is high, and cadmium ions can be detected using the Cadion IREA reagent.

Results: To determine cadmium ions, technogenic water samples belonging to the Mubarak gas processing plant located in the Kashkadarya region were used, and the amount of cadmium was determined by the introduction-recovery method.

Table 1

Results of spectrophotometric determination of cadmium (II) ions from wastewater from the Mubarak gas processing plant (n=5; P=0.95)

Me ₂₊	Entered, mg/l	Found, mg/l	S	S _r
Cd ²⁺	1,00	1,0±0,04	0,076	0,052
	1,50	1,54±0,06	0,055	0,038
	2,00	2,05±0,09	0,083	0,04

The results show that in the sorption-spectroscopic determination of cadmium ion, the value of S did not exceed 0.083, and the value of S_r did not exceed 0.52. This allows the method to determine cadmium ions in environmental samples.

Conclusion: The developed method allows the determination of cadmium ions, and the mechanisms of complex formation between the cation IREA reagent and cadmium ions were studied. The optimal environment for the reaction, the influence of foreign ions, and the reaction ratios were determined. The small values of S and S_r indicate that the method can be widely used.

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